

OFX-OFX vs CTRL GO CC Enrichment Analysis

Upregulated | Significant genes: 194 | Top 4 pathways

$-\log_{10} p.\text{adj}$

0 3 6 9

Gene Count

● 5 ● 10 ● 15 ● 20 ● 25 ● 30